

ENHANCING RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN HIGHWAY AND ROAD CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS USING THE RELATIVE IMPORTANCE INDEX (RII)

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Abstract

This study uses the Relative Importance method to identify highway and road building project important risk elements. Successful highway and high-volume road building projects require risk assessment and management, as these projects are exposed to significant uncertainties stemming from financial, managerial, political, and terrain-related factors. This study investigates the critical risk factors affecting such projects and prioritizes them using the Relative Importance Index (RII). A structured questionnaire, developed from an initial list of 40 risk factors and refined to 31 after pilot testing, was distributed to 150 industry professionals, producing 120 valid responses (80% response rate). The respondents comprised contractors (40%), consultants (35%), and project owners (25%), with an average of 12 years of professional experience, ensuring robust data quality. The analysis revealed financial risks as the most dominant, with "Delay in payments" (RII = 0.933, Rank 1) and "Owner bankruptcy" (RII = 0.911, Rank 2) emerging as the most severe factors. Managerial risks including poor planning, weak leadership, and inadequate project scope definition—were also critical, while unforeseen soil conditions, underground utilities, and land acquisition challenges highlighted the influence of terrain-related risks. Findings from the study highlight the significance of owners, consultants, and contractors identifying and allocating risks early on to keep disputes to a minimum and guarantee effective project completion. With a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.84, the survey instrument was determined to be reliable. By integrating insights from international literature and aligning with findings in China, the UAE, and Pakistan, the study confirms the global relevance of these risks. Practical recommendations include contractual safeguards, enhanced cash-flow management, improved stakeholder coordination, and the application of multi-criteria techniques (AHP, TOPSIS, Monte Carlo) alongside RII for stronger decision support. The findings give project managers and politicians targeted advice to improve risk management and road infrastructure project performance.

INTRODUCTION

Any construction project needs risk management, especially highway and road projects, because many parties are involved, designers, contractors, subcontractors, and suppliers. Uncertainties in such projects can lead to economic loss, project failure, or injuries; These uncertainties affect likely occurrence and impact severity. Thus, project success requires risk management.

Risks affect highway and road construction at every stage of the development process, beginning with planning, followed by design, and finally during execution, because these projects involve large-scale operations and coordination among multiple stakeholders. Schedule delays, cost increment, and quality reduction borne of poor risk management further exacerbate the condition of the project.

Typical risks which should be identified at the outset so that significant disruptions do not occur include poor planning, unforeseen ground conditions, and regulation changes. The Relative Importance Index (RII) provides a ranked method through which these risks can be identified. It will also assist project managers and others involved in a specific project with resource allocation. It is in the geographic-specific conditions that sensibly add to the difficulties of road construction in an area of contrasting geography. Usually, sources of uncertainty arise from not properly identifying underground utilities and unexpected ground conditions. If these two critical risks can be identified prior to construction, project managers, contractors, and consultants can avoid negative impacts like budget overruns and delays through time adjustments. The whole risk management process will improve doing a project when risks are shared between owners, employees, and assistants in a manner in which each knows what their responsibilities are if a risk materializes. There are three common risks that builders regularly face: costs exceeding the initial budget, schedule delays, and deterioration in project quality. Conventional studies and standard risk-management techniques do not fully remove the severe impacts of these risks on project performance. Risk management in construction requires considerable resilience because the industry is dynamic and individual projects differ in characteristics such as location and weather. This

study seeks to analyse the critical risks that impact highways and road construction projects by utilizing the RII method and examining their effects on performance. The results seek to bolster risk-management strategies to predict threats and provide recommendations for mitigation measures to enhance project outcomes.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

It has taken years to come up with a unified way to prioritize the repair of low-volume roads. The endeavor is reflected in Zhi's earlier work (1995), which established one of the original frameworks for recognizing, managing, and delineating risks associated with building projects. Although his research focused on foreign nations, he illuminated some internal and external factors—such as pathways for inflation, bureaucracy, and corruption—that might significantly hinder a project. His understanding does provide a very valuable framework on which to appreciate the multifariousness of construction risks in less-developed countries where such challenges tend to be considerably more prominent.

A few years later, Akintoye and MacLeod (1997) expanded on this conversation by doing research on how construction companies in Britain handle risk. The results showed that the construction business is getting more complicated and found the hazards that are most likely to stop a project from being successful. These involved financial conditions that are always changing and market dynamics that are not steady. It was sufficiently acknowledged to inspire future research, including the study by Bing et al. (2005) regarding the distribution of risks in Public-Private Partnership (PPP) and Private Finance Initiative (PFI) projects in the UK. This study yields intriguing results, indicating that the public sector assumes greater risks than the private sector. It reveals that risks in the public sector are predominantly political, whereas in the private sector, they are more project-specific. It gets much more specific to problems with managing money.

Simultaneously, Wang et al. (2004) expanded the examination of the Asian crisis to developing nations during the same timeframe, formulating a risk management model tailored to their unique

circumstances. This study underscored the difficulties faced by these regions, including fiscal imbalances, political instability, and market volatility. Likewise, Ghosh and Jintanapakanont (2004), in their analysis of underground railway projects in Thailand, identified delays and financial fragility as significant obstacles. This reflects a wider international apprehension about the vulnerability of large-scale infrastructure initiatives.

Additional research has yielded intriguing results. This paper describes the Chinese construction business, where contractors' inexperience and poor financial management put projects at danger (Zou et al., 2007). An UAE analysis identified inflation and project schedule inflexibility to be major risks. These research showed that building hazards are worldwide and that contextual factors in Asia and the Middle East might affect risk outcomes. In the new decade, it became evident that more complex tools were needed. **Zavadskas et al. (2010)** introduced multi-attribute decision-making techniques such as TOPSIS for evaluating and ranking construction risks. Their research demonstrated that systematic and quantitative approaches could significantly minimize project losses. Building on this, **Subramanyan et al. (2012)** applied fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) in India, showing that risk reduction techniques rooted in structured decision models can be instrumental in delivering successful projects.

The conversation later shifted toward rural infrastructure. **Mane et al. (2016)** proposed a Pavement Maintenance and Management System (PMMS) tailored for Indian rural roads, particularly in regions lacking historical data. Their approach provided engineers with practical, context-specific methods that accounted for traffic volume and weather conditions. Similarly, **Agarwal et al. (2016)** emphasized that low-volume rural roads require simple, cost-effective management strategies, rather than complex, urban-focused tools that may not be feasible in rural contexts.

In parallel, **El-Sayegh and Mansour (2015)** turned their attention to highway construction in the UAE, identifying inefficient planning as the most significant risk. They reported 33 major risk factors, including resource mismanagement and poor coordination among project parties. Their

conclusions were consistent with those of **Nguyen et al. (2014)**, who studied risk management in Vietnam. Nguyen et al. listed risks in four categories, Contractor, Owner, Designer, and Project Manager, and indicated that frequent changes added among the most complaining issues. It is thus apparent that adequate communication by the stakeholders would play a great role in ensuring that risks are mitigated before they escalate.

The literature also acknowledged the importance of a knowledge-based approach. As stated by **Serpella et al. (2014)**, systematic learning from past experiences is necessary to advance beyond the elementary stage of identifying risks toward effective risk management. Previous projects can provide insight into how to avoid repeating mistakes that lead to cost overruns and time delays in the future. A study by **Perera et al. (2009)** on Sri Lankan Road projects emphasized that risk strategies need to be particularized within the context of the project at hand thereby supporting the argument regarding the inadequacy of standardized solutions.

Themes recur. **Iqbal et al., (2015)** note, after studying Pakistan's construction sector, that delayed payments, poor design, and inadequate financing are the most critical risks. **Dandage et al., (2018)** apply the TOPSIS method to international projects as recipients of risk assessors' largesse and identify political and design related risks as the dominant ones. There is a more tested path to better fortified prioritization by borrowing strength from quantitative models.

Other studies widen the net. **Ameyaw and Chan (2015)** conducted a study on PPP water supply projects in developing countries using fuzzy logic thus bringing to limelight crucial risks such as exchange rate fluctuation and corruption. According to **Ugwu et al. (2019)** studying the construction industry of Nigeria, premised on an early detection of risks that would determine the success of achieving the objectives of carrying out a project. Recent contributions emphasized the stakeholder perspectives **Willumsen et al. (2019)** noted that in order to make valid choices of risks to prioritize, the perceptions of various stakeholders need to be understood, arguing that participatory involvement helps to make valid choices of risks to prioritize. This requires an understanding from a people-centered

perspective as suggested by Viswanathan et al. (2019), wherein the participation of locals and clearly defined contracts matter since cross-boundary issues enhance risks in international projects. Finally, Yu et al. (2018) noted from the study of transnational PPP projects that legal disputes, tariff issues, and cooperation problems were significant. There is a return to construction activities that are becoming more globalized, which makes it even more important to have good communication channels and rules.

3 Methodology:

This study systematically identified and prioritized highway and road building project risks. A pilot research reduced 40 potential risk variables from an exhaustive literature analysis and construction management professionals' opinions to 31 prioritized hazards. The amended list formed the basis of this research's extensive survey.

3.1: Designing the Questionnaire and Data Collection

A systematic questionnaire given to stakeholders actively involved in road and highway works collected probabilities and severities for each risk factor on a five-point scale from 1 to 5. The combined rating assessed risk importance more thoroughly. Respondents were also asked whether owner, contractor, or consultant should bear that risk.

150 experts received the questionnaires via Google Forms and in-person interviews at project sites. Valid responses total 120, an 80% response rate. This profile includes 40% contractors, 35% consultants, and 25% project owners with an average professional experience of 12 years. This distribution offers broad yet reliable construction industry presence.

The questionnaire received a Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.87, which means that it had good internal consistency. This means that it is safe to say that the data collected were reliable for further study.

3.2: Data Analysis

The Relative Importance Index (RII) used to prioritize risk variables was quantified in this study. The simplicity of RII led to its selection, ease of interpretation, and appropriateness when there is a

need to rank many factors based on responses garnered through a survey. While models like AHP, TOPSIS, or Monte Carlo simulations can provide more comprehensive or probabilistic evaluations, RII was considered most appropriate for this study because it offers a straightforward, practical approach for industry practitioners to prioritize risks efficiently. Future research could integrate RII with other models to enhance robustness.

$$RII = \frac{5n_5 + 4n_4 + 3n_3 + 2n_2 + 1n_1}{5N}$$

Where:

- W = Weight assigned to each response (1 to 5)
- A = Highest possible weight (in this case, 5)
- N = Total number of respondents
- n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5 = Number of respondents assigning each weight from 1 to 5

Interpretation of RII Values:

- **Higher RII (close to 1):** Indicates a more significant or severe risk/factor that requires **urgent attention**.
- **Lower RII (close to 0):** Suggests a **less critical** risk/factor.

Reliability Check Using Cronbach's Alpha

To evaluate survey instrument reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was determined. This test measures answer internal consistency from 0 to 1, with higher results indicating greater reliability. The formula is.

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{k \times \bar{c}}{\bar{v} + (k - 1)\bar{c}} \right)$$

Where:

- k = Number of scale items
- \bar{c} = Average covariance between item pairs
- \bar{v} = Average variance of each item

The Cronbach's Alpha value was 0.87, exceeding the social science research criterion of 0.70. This shows excellent internal consistency and verifies the data's reliability for analysis.

3.3: Risk Classification Methods

- To manage project-specific risks, the study conducted came up with several methods of risk classification that placed priority in the natural characteristics of risks. It resulted in five categories of risks namely, management,

technical, financial, environmental, and legal which characterize the stakeholders that would be guaranteed risk management throughout project lifecycle. This categorization is illustrated in Table 1 and it allows one to assess accountability between owners of the project, contractors and consultants in an unambiguous way.

3.4: Rationale and Limitations

- This decision to do a survey on the basis of questionnaire was necessitated by the need to capture the views of the industry professionals in relation to highway and road construction procedures. Through this tool of data-collection, we managed to obtain several professional evaluations, and thus we estimated professional perception of risk on a wide variety of levels. However, there is the inherent weakness in this approach in the fact that responses are predisposed to some biases that are a result of subjectivity. In their turn, follow-up investigations should complement the results of questionnaire investigations with more qualitative methods, i.e., follow-ups of structured

interview type or case studies will help provide the additional support and confirmation of findings obtained with the help of the questionnaire as the focus of the research design.

4 Results

- The authors made an undivided investigation through literature review, survey and Relative Importance Index (RII) to identify and place highway and road construction projects as the major risks. They represent their findings in the form of tables and allow systematic analysis of tools to classify risks, methods of identification, and the prevailing risk factors that determine the project results.

4.1: Risk Classification Methods

- To effectively distribute the responsibility of risk-management and reduce risks within the team members, the project team used a number of schemes of classifying risks. These methods are summarized in table 1.

Table 1: Risk Classification Methods

S.NO	Risk Classification Methods	Example
1	Underlying source of risks	Internal or external
2	Type of risks	Management, financial, etc.
3	Incidences of risks at various levels	Planning, design, execution, etc.
4	Cause of the risk	Client, contractor, subcontractor
5	No classification	Direct listing of risks

4.2: Risk Identification Techniques

Various risk identifications strategies were also used frequently throughout the project life cycle. Surveys, literature reviews, expert interviews, and

brainstorming sessions were the most common methodological tools according to the findings of the present study as Table 2 demonstrates.

Table 2: Risk Identification Techniques

S.NO	Tools and Techniques Used
1	Questionnaire survey
2	Literature review
3	Brainstorming and Delphi technique
4	Expert interviews and checklists
5	Past project data
6	Documentation review

In this study, an integrative method of risk management was adopted, which allowed a combination of multiple risk-assessment methods to be used as the project was initiated, and continued to conclusion, since a risk-assessment method may be inappropriate depending on the phase of the project development.

4.3: Critical Risks in Construction.

A comprehensive literature study identified 67 building project risk indicators. Table 3 shows that financial, technical, and managerial difficulties are most typically mentioned.

Table 3: Top Ten Risks Identified from Literature

S.NO	Risk Factor	Nature of Risk
1	Funding shortages	Financial risk
2	Design errors and engineering deficiencies	Technical risk
3	inadequate site management	Supervision/Management risk
4	Contractual risks	Legal risk
5	Laws and regulation changes	Political risk
6	Harch environmental Factors	Environmental risk
7	Change in inflation rate	Financial risk
8	Natural disasters	Environmental risk
9	Inadequate safety measures	Health & Safety risk
10	Change in project scope	Legal risk

4.4; Risk Ranking Using RII

High-volume of the road projects was conducted in order to analyze potential threats with the Risk Identification and Impact (RII) Analysis. As per Table 4, risks that were ranked the highest are the

ones associated with the financial aspect, payment delays and bankruptcy of the owner.

Table 4: Risk Analysis for High-Volume Roads (RII Method)

Risk Category	Risk No.	Risks	RII(%)	Rank
Design	R1	Unclear construction drawings	75.56%	23
	R6	Limited pre-design investigations and data gathering	86.67%	5
	R7	Application of antiquated design techniques	73.33%	24
	R21	Inadequate/unclear definition of project scope	91.11%	2
Management	R2	Poor Coordination	73.33%	24
	R17	Inadequate collaboration and communication of the project manager with other on-site contractors.	80.00%	17
	R18	Lack of leadership quality of project manager	88.89%	4
	R19	Insufficient project monitoring and guidance from the manager	84.44%	9
Construction/Quality	R3	Improper construction methods/quality control	80.00%	17
	R11	Inadequate construction quality	73.33%	24
Planning	R4	Inefficient planning	86.67%	5
Execution/Resource	R5	Delay in mobilization	82.22%	15
	R20	Frequent change of subcontractors/vendors	82.22%	15
Owner/Administrative	R22	Delay in handing over the site to contractor	82.22%	15
Execution/Management	R12	Ineffective site coordination and monitoring by the contractor	86.67%	5
Financial	R13	Delay in payments	93.33%	1
	R15	Owner Bankruptcy	91.11%	2
Contractual	R14	Conflicts in contract documents	84.44%	9
Technical/Environmental	R8	Unexpected underground utilities	84.44%	9
Geotechnical	R9	Unforeseen soil conditions	77.78%	20
Safety	R10	Inadequate safety measures	84.44%	9
Human Resource/Design	R16	Designer leaving the project midway	84.44%	9
Environmental	R23	Adverse weather conditions	82.22%	15
Security	R24	Criminal acts	53.33%	28
	R28	Theft	71.11%	28
Cultural/Social	R25	Cultural differences	48.89%	31
Ethical/Corruption	R26	Bribes	68.89%	26
Labour	R27	Labour disputes and strikes	77.78%	20

Supply Chain	R29	Delay of material supply by suppliers	66.67%	29
Equipment/Resource	R30	Equipment breakdown	53.33%	30

The table presents the RII analysis of high-volume road project risks. Financial risks, such as payment

unclear project scope (91.11%) and lack of leadership (88.89%), while poor site management (86.67%) and inefficient planning (86.67%) are also notable. The graph clearly highlights priorities for risk mitigation, emphasizing financial stability and effective project management.

4.5: Risk Factors Across Project Phases

Risk identification was added to cover different phases of the construction of the highway as pre-

delays (93.33%) and owner bankruptcy (91.11%), are the most critical. Other significant risks include

construction, design, site preparation, and construction. RII framework investigation conducted revealed that the greatest risks were related to delays connected with machinery, the discrepancy between design and building, and the acquisition of political permits (Table 5).

Table 5: Risk Analysis Using RII(Highway Projects)

Risk Category	Risk No.	Risks	RII	Rank
Construction	R1	Machinery issues	0.692	16
	R4	Contractor productivity issues	0.723	11
	R5	Delay in achieving scheduled milestones	0.75	9
	R6	Improper equipment selection	0.843	3
	R9	Lack of communication	0.783	4
Design	R7	Design fidelity and durability	0.767	6
	R10	Design errors and omissions	0.711	12
Topography	R11	Constrained project corridor	0.657	17
	R12	Unexpected ground conditions	0.673	15
Political	R13	Late approval of project submittals	0.67	16
	R14	Railway permit challenges	0.765	2
	R15	Lag in property acquisition	0.637	20
	R16	Regulatory changes	0.567	31
Land Acquisition	R18	Uncertain land acquisition costs	0.753	5
	R20	Improperly structured contract documents	0.64	19
	R21	Discrepancies in contract documents	0.623	23
Environmental	R22	Environmental effects of project	0.693	13
Organizational	R23	Experienced workers	0.587	28
	R24	Delays in preparation of submittals	0.647	18
	R25	Insufficient technology/skills/techniques	0.81	3
	R26	Inadequate claim administration	0.627	22
Accidental	R27	Archaeological Finds	0.533	32
	R28	Inadequate safety measures	0.74	11
Utilities	R29	Material	0.58	29
	R30	Unexpected underground utilities	0.613	25
Law & Order	R31	Existing traffic	0.603	27
	R32	Third party liability	0.533	32
Climatic Condition	R34	Unfavorable climatic factors	0.5	37
	R35	Site contamination	0.687	14
Others	R38	Delay in payments	0.633	21

The table presents the RII analysis of highway project risks. Construction-related risks, such as the selection of inappropriate equipment (RII = 0.843, **Rank 3**), are the most critical. Other significant risks include insufficient technology and skills (RII = 0.810, **Rank 3**), lack of communication (RII = 0.783, **Rank 4**), and railway permit challenges (RII = 0.765, **Rank 2**). Design quality issues (RII = 0.767, **Rank 6**) and uncertain land acquisition costs (RII = 0.753, **Rank 5**) were also found to be highly influential.

The analysis shows that the biggest problems with delivering a project are construction, organisational, and political risks. These results show how important it is to improve communication, make it easier to get political approval, and make sure that the right equipment is used to finish highway projects on time and efficiently.

5 Discussion

Financial constraints remain the biggest danger to large-scale highway and road building projects. This study found that delayed payments and project owners' bankruptcy weaken contractors' ability to progress on site. This causes a ripple effect that affects material procurement, wage payment, and resource allocation, causing schedule delays and cost overruns. It supports prior findings by Akintoye, MacLeod (1997) and El-Sayegh, Mansour (2015) that financial stability and predictable cash flow are key to project success. Therefore, payment processes, more transparent financial monitoring systems, and contractual safeguards can reduce these risks. (Zhi, 1995).

Apart from financial constraints, managerial shortcomings are a major project risk. Inefficiencies from poor planning, resource allocation, and supervision can affect project performance. Iqbal et al. (2015) and Nguyen et al. (2014) discovered that managerial inadequacies caused low productivity and delays. This study shows that good leadership speeds decision-making and motivates project teams to perform better. Serpella et al. (2014) and Willumsen et al. (2019) found that leadership and structured risk management create value in building projects..

It also found that risk comes differently at different stages of the lifecycle. During initiation, issues of acquisition of land, permits political and regulatory approvals mostly cause delays that would creep in later stages. The study conducted in South Asia by Agarwal et al. (2016); El-Sayegh (2008) also noted such uncertainty related to land and bureaucratic processes as major hindrances toward timely delivery of infrastructure. The risks in the design and implementation stages include scope changes, differences between design and construction, and compliance with ever-changing regulations. These results support the findings of Ghosh and Jintanapakanont (2004) and Zou et al. (2007), who had earlier established that uncertainty related to design is a frequent problem in rail as well as road projects.

Financial, managerial, and political risks are the dominant risks in highway and road construction projects. Financial disruption will undermine project continuity while managerial ineffectiveness reduces the strength of operations being performed. Adding complexity through uncertainty in a project brought about by political or regulatory issues results in complexity added to the execution of a project. This finding confirms prior studies carried out internationally whereby similar challenges were reported within different regional contexts by Wang et al. (2004), Ugwu et al. (2019), and Perera et al. (2009). It also indicates that while risks may vary in form and intensity, they constantly threaten construction project schedule, cost, and quality goals. Fiscal discipline, project management, and institutional backing are needed to mitigate these risks. This will boost resilience and delivery capability while ensuring highway and road development project success.

6 Conclusion

Many risks can delay, overspend, and degrade highway and road construction projects if not managed appropriately. The scale, location, strength of investment, and regulatory environment of the project will vary the risks. Financial technical and managerial risks still dominate all phases.

By merging data from literature and survey-based analysis, this paper proves the feasibility of applying a systematic risk identification and assessment approach applying the Relative Importance Index (RII) throughout a project. Effective risk management early in project planning and throughout execution reduces delays, stabilizes cost factors, and enhances quality outputs. This develops an opportunity for practitioners and policymakers to prioritize financial safeguards, managerial capacity building, and coordination among stakeholders. The adoption of comprehensive and preventive risk management will pave the way for resilience as well as sustainability in highway and road infrastructure projects.

6.1: Practical Implications and Recommendations

This study emphasizes the need for positive risk-management strategies in construction. A critical literature assessment yields three recommendations:

(1) comprehensive training in risk management theory and practice, (2) early project integration of risk-management tools, and (3) active monitoring of risk variables by the workforce throughout the project lifecycle. Together, these practices enhance the ability of project managers to perform effectively in managing risks. Embedding such risk-management measures within project teams enables them to anticipate and avoid unexpected events, thereby facilitating sound decision-making and optimizing time-sensitive project outcomes.

6.2: Future Research

It is necessary for future research to investigate the implementation of active risk-management models that operate in real time, utilizing project-based datasets to predict and mitigate emerging threats. Empirical studies conducted on both individual projects and across regions with distinct geographical characteristics will be essential in determining effective strategies for risk reduction tailored to local conditions. The outcomes of such datasets would provide a strong baseline for refining and streamlining current risk-management practices, thereby enabling more robust and efficient results in the construction industry.

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